

THE INFLUENCE OF AXOLOGICAL PEDAGOGY AND EDUCATIONAL ORIENTATIONS ON STUDENTS' WORLDVIEW

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The changes taking place in society have intensified the search for new, vital values for young people, ways to include them in the educational process.

The formation of pedagogical axiology as a methodological approach in understanding pedagogical phenomena contributes to the solution of the problem of overcoming the cultural crisis and the development of the human value sphere.

The axiological approach is organically inherent in modern pedagogy, in which the pupil is considered in it as the highest value of society. In this regard, axiology can be considered as the methodological basis of education and modern pedagogy. The works of B.M. Bim-Bada, B.S. Brushlinsky, B.I. Dodonova, B.G. Kuznetsova, N.D. Nikandrova, V.A. Slastenina, V.M. Rozina, M.N. Fisher, P.G. Shchedrovitsky and others.

The central concept in axiology is the concept of value, which characterizes the socio-cultural significance of the phenomena of reality included in value relations. The latter are formed because of a person's distinction between good and evil, truth and error, beautiful and ugly, and other culturally significant characteristics of reality. These aspects of general axiology should also be taken into account when developing pedagogical axiology. Pedagogical reality as part of the social includes the whole set of specific pedagogical phenomena, which are united by their belonging to the purposeful process of human education. This includes the subjects of this process themselves (educators and pupils), the content and process of education, various forms, methods and means of education. In general, the problem of criteria for the value of phenomena in pedagogical axiology needs serious theoretical research.

The value maturity of the teacher himself determines the effectiveness of interaction with students in mastering the values they need, the desire or unwillingness to follow the example of the teacher, purposefully work on oneself. Management of the efforts and capabilities of pupils remains in the hands of a mentor, correctly oriented in axiological terms. Moreover, this should become in the modern pedagogical process not an accidental, but a systematic and purposeful thing. Knowledge that has not been turned into values by the

efforts of teachers and not mastered by the student precisely as values is easily forgotten and never becomes a meaning-forming factor.

Pedagogical axiology largely changes the nature of the interaction between the teacher and the student. The focus is not just knowledge, skills, habits or the formation of some habits in the student, but a whole range of vital values, the formation of his need to appropriate them, to live by them. The school begins directly to teach the pupil the ability confidently navigate the world around him, perfectly distinguish its qualitative, and value heterogeneity. The degree of development of such a skill in a schoolchild becomes one of the most important indicators of the level of his upbringing.

Because of the categorical apparatus of general axiology, a thesaurus of pedagogical axiology is formed, the essence of which is determined by the specifics of pedagogical activity, its social role and personality-forming opportunities. Pedagogical values not only allow meeting the needs of the teacher, but also serve as guidelines for his social and professional activity aimed at achieving humanistic goals.

Pedagogical values, like any others, are not approved spontaneously. They depend on social, political, economic relations in society, which largely determine the development of pedagogy and educational practice. Moreover, this dependence is not mechanical, because what is desired and necessary at the level of society often comes into conflict, which a particular person, a teacher, resolves on the basis of his worldview, ideals, choosing ways to reproduce and develop culture.

The presented classification allows the most complete systematization of the professional values of a modern teacher. However, it is necessary to note the conditional nature of the classification, the versatility and interdependence of the distinguished groups of values.

N. D. Shaniyazov identifies the following values: values associated with approval in society, the immediate environment; values associated with meeting the need for communication; values associated with self-improvement; values associated with self-expression; values associated with utilitarian-pragmatic needs.

We tried to classify the entire generalized nomenclature of professional pedagogical values based on their significance in the professional development of a teacher.

For students of a pedagogical university, the most significant are the following values: Humanistic values of pedagogical activity: The student is the personality of the student as the highest value in the educational process. Value guidelines

determine human behavior, and a value attitude towards a student is a condition for the development of the subjective principle in him and forms the basis for ensuring students' readiness for personal self-determination.

Childhood is a unique, valuable period of life that differs from an adult, a special culture characterized by a holistic worldview, openness to the world, sensitivity, emotionality, and spontaneity. Childhood is the main value. Premature growing up is not an achievement, but a misfortune, skipping stages or periods of child development that have enduring value. Child psychologist A. Zaporozhets warned about unreasonable haste and artificial forcing of children's development. On the contrary, he cared about the enrichment of each period of age development.

The uniqueness and individuality of the individual. It is a miracle that each individual is different from all. Individuality, as such, has an ideal value character and is understood as a set of semantic relations and attitudes of a person in the world, which are appropriated in the course of life in society, provide orientation in the hierarchy of values and mastery of behavior in a situation of struggle of motives.

Student development. The concept of pedagogical professionalism is considered in the context of the extent to which a teacher can develop the subjective potential of students, provide the conditions for his personal growth (V. V. Davydov, V. A. Korotov, N. D. Nikandrov, A. V. Mudrik, Yu. B. Orlov, V. A. Slastenin, I. S. Yakimanskaya). Nevertheless, this is possible only on the condition that the child's personal development is included in the teacher's system of professional value orientations, and, in turn, will be largely determined by those criteria for evaluating the teacher's work, the system of value orientations adopted in the teaching staff.

Self-realization of the student. The leading need of both the teacher and the student is the need for self-realization. However, there is a contradiction between the teacher's desire for self-realization and his orientation towards the formation of students' ability to creative self-realization. The teacher's lack of awareness that his self-realization gains meaning only through the development of students' ability for creative self-realization leads to the results of pedagogical activity that are inadequate in terms of the development of cognitive, ethical, axiological, phraseological relations in children, which form the content of creative self-realization.

It can be argued that values are capable of changing attitudes towards forms of action, freeing them from the power of a particular situation. Values as a

phenomenon of the ideal have energy activity and "exist" in activity. In other words, ideal images are realized in activity. Therefore, new pedagogical and managerial technologies are, first, the adoption of a new look at the child (at the person), at the meaning of education. Everything else is just an imitation of innovations in education. "Value orientations" also do not have an unambiguous interpretation and are considered as conscious beliefs or ideas of the subject about what is valuable for him, as a form of existence of values.

In conclusion, we emphasize that the need for pedagogical axiology has matured, and its development as a part of pedagogical innovation is now necessary.

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